

Effects of a Shintergy-sinchronized brain over a laser beam: Present time, close proximity.

José Luis Bueno-Ramos BSc^{1*} | Arturo Ortiz-Tapia PhD^{1*}

| Inés Urdaneta PhD^{2, 1*} | Alan Armando

Aguero-Rojas-Vertiz MSc^{1*}

¹Hypatia Research Institute Mexico SC Av Nuevo León 213 Despacho 503-3 Hipódromo Condesa, Cdmx 06140

²Hawaii Institute for Unified Physics, Kailua Kona, Hawaii, 96740, USA

Correspondence

* Department of Mathematics and Theoretical Physics, Hypatia Research Institute Mexico SC Av Nuevo León 213 Despacho 503-3 Hipódromo Condesa, Cdmx 06140
Email: egl.arturo.ortizta@unadmexico.mx

Funding information

For 1) Hypatia Research Institute Mexico SC Av Nuevo León 213 Despacho 503-3 Hipódromo Condesa, Cdmx 06140; For 2) Hawaii Institute for Unified Physics, Kailua Kona, Hawaii, 96740, USA

1 | INTRODUCTION

"[...] it is inherent in human consciousness to notice some facts about the things one is doing" [15].

Possibly one of the earliest mention of the concept of consciousness is related with Samyutta Nikaya 22.79 [26]: "And why do you call it 'consciousness'? Because it cognizes, thus it is called consciousness. What does it cognize? It cognizes what is sour, bitter, pungent, sweet, alkaline, non-alkaline, salty, & unsalty. Because it cognizes, it is called consciousness."

In the Upanishads [9] consciousness is not described in terms of what it is, but rather on what the states of it are, namely,

Strong correlations are found between brain activity of a subject in close proximity both in time and space, performing Shintergy-like synchronization under controlled conditions, and measurements made with a 100mW, 532nm laser.

KEYWORDS

Shintergy, synchronization, altered states of consciousness

* Equally contributing authors.

1. The waking state (bahish-prajnya)
2. The dreaming mind (antah-prajnya)
3. Deep sleep (suṣupti),
4. Pure consciousness (Turiya),

Intelligence has been related, if not used equivalently, to consciousness [15], and precisely because it is difficult to describe in operational terms what consciousness is, consciousness has been related to self-awareness, cognition and similar concepts [21], including the problem of free will [8].

On the side of physics there has been some attempts to show that consciousness (and related concepts) is a emergent property of a self-organized biological system [2] or any system, given a cumulative underlying logical recursivity [15].

Certainly one aspect of consciousness is the question concerning of "action at a distance", which at the very least has been useful to further research of fundamental physics [14]. Action at a distance, as has been used in physics, has also been suggested in context of so-called "quantum mysticism" [6], without giving much (if at all) operational foundations to work with.

In this work it is presented an operational definition of consciousness, based on the assumptions made by current knowledge of physiology of consciousness, quantum mechanics and relativity, which is then put to test experimentally, and the results ultimately related with the structure of the universe at large, through the concept of dark matter, exhibiting that consciousness and its varied manifestations, herein defined, must be pervasive at all scales, and all directions of space-time. Dark matter and dark energy have had attempts of explanations using different kinds of assumptions [28], including the possible omission of N-body effects [25]. As it will be seen, the experimental results rather point towards the collapse of a bosonic field, which create both the curvature of space-time and what consciousness itself, at least in the way that is herein defined.

With all the above and under an objective and critical focus, this research emerges with the precise question: *Can the Shintergy synchronization be observed and what would be its implications as an interaction, with clear effects on the light of a laser beam, gravity expressed as a change in the measures of a weight scale, and thus possibly some alteration of space-time?*

2 | METHODOLOGY

2.1 | Experimental set-up for the physical measurements

The whole strategy of the physical measurements while on Shyntergy-synchronization is driven by the idea that consciousness has physical manifestations, and thus it should be measurable, in particular using a laser beam according to a planned, but unexecuted, experiment thought by Jacobo Greenberg [4]. The laser device was connected to an Arduino electronic control tablet, and the Arduino program compiler [16].

In the following sections the design and construction of the equipment is going to be briefly described.

2.1.1 | Laser

A 100mW, 532nm laser, activated in continuous mode, was fixed on the extreme of a mounting that allow fine-tune of the supporting legs through screws. At the other side it was fixed a photocell (as a laser beam profiler) which regis-

tered any variation of brilliancy from the laser, rendering low numbers for high brilliancy, and bigger numbers for any increase of darkness. Between the laser beam and the said photocell, a focusing device was fixed, which consist of a hollow tube with a small perforation on one side, so that the laser beam arrives mostly within the diameter of the photocell (Fig.2).

The photocell is connected to an Arduino circuit, which in turn is connected to a computer (see paragraphs below for detailed explanation), where an Arduino program may be started to begin the registration of the measurements, until the Arduino plaque is disconnected, to allow the manual transcription of the collected measurements towards a spreadsheet. The strategy was that if the Shintergy synchronization could have any influence whatsoever, this would be registered as variations of the brilliancy. However, after the first experiments were made, it was clear that further devices were needed, to attempt to assert the nature of the phenomenon that made the brilliancy change. It is known that loss of received brilliancy would imply a loss of photons, which in turn usually can be ascribed to optical phenomena [23].

Under the development of the proper equipment for the laser experiment, the following principal points were taken into consideration (Fig.1):

FIGURE 1 Design mind-map.

Body Frame

With the help of a CAD software (Siemens NX 12) a model of the 1/2 inch galvanised pipe frame was design in such a way to hold the laser, filter the incoming beam of light and support the photoelectric resistor. The principal idea for which galvanised pipe was used as material for the construction of the system it is the great work versatility and stiffness of the material. These not only allowed the system to have a strong hold of the equipment but at the same time gives the possibility of adjustment on an irregular surface, this thanks to the pipe threading on the entire design (Fig.2).

FIGURE 2 Body frame.

Electronics

The integration of the electronics systems for the data acquisition was based on four main components which are

- Arduino
- Laser
- Resistor
- Photo-Resistor

Using a common resistance and photo-resistor, a voltage divider was created (Fig.3a). Based upon this electric principle, it was possible for the Arduino to read the analog signal values coming from the photo-resistor and convert them into digital ones able to be analyzed into a computer connected to the Arduino's serial port (Fig.3b). These

values range from 0 to 1023 accordingly to the range voltage from 0 to 5 volts coming out from the photo-resistor (Fig.3).

FIGURE 3 Circuitry for laser detection.

It is important to note that the impedance of the photo resistor increases as the photon intensity decreases. This can be expressed with the following mathematical expression

$$I_p \propto \frac{1}{R} \tag{1}$$

By Ohms Law, we can say that $V \propto R$; therefore

$$I_p \propto \frac{1}{V_{out}} \tag{2}$$

This design implication has a deep meaning in the test result, as can be seen by the above equations, the Arduino analog input registers high values as the photo-resistor register losses in photon intensity. The voltage across the photo-resistor can be easily obtained with the next equation below

$$V_{out} = \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2} V_{in} \tag{3}$$

Programming

Two different sets of programming codes where design, one was made on the Arduino programming language and the other on Excel Macros. These two codes were planned to work together in such a way that Arduino would collect the data from the photo-resistor and then transfer that information to an Excel spread sheet. This was planned to analyzed the data in a cleaner and easier way.

2.2 | The synchronization technique

Shintergy is a paradigm, a model and a methodology of human neuro-engineering and high performance, with 25 years of development in clinical and field research by the psychologist José Luis Bueno since 1995 in different environments

and populations [5].

The brain-mind Shintergy-synchronization (henceforth referred to just as Shintergy) is focused in a complex range of perception and its interaction with the different levels of density, of what is now understood to be the quantum vacuum and the quantum field, through a simultaneous perception similar to contemplation [17] and that goes much further than conventional meditative states [17] with a single focusing point (unipunctual).

Shintergy has emerged as a *synergy* from the following elements:

1. Jacobo Grinberg's Sintergic theory [11], received in collaboration and researched with Dr. Jacobo Grinberg
2. The Fracto-Holographic theory of Nassim Haramein and its approach about vacuum fluctuations with the spherical unit of vacuum. [13, 12]
3. The methodology, practice and activations from 20 years of brain training with teachers from Dzogchen of Tibetan Yungdrung Bon and other Tibetan Dzogchen teachers. [24]
4. The practice and perspective of Hindu Advaita.
5. The psycho-corporal perspective of somatology from Alfonso Caycedo and David Parra. [7]
6. The psycho-corporal integration of high performance exercises about perception, taken from ancient cultures, namely, Mexican, Chinese, Tibetan, African and Hindu.
7. The SHIN model integrated by Jose Luis Bueno (one of the authors) derived from Yan Xin Qigong [27], focused on the individual and collective learning and development of potential.
8. The systemic perspective and the paradigm of medicine and traditional culture from China and Mexico. [22]
9. The integral perspective of clinical psychology and a unified vision of the main five currents of psychology (psychoanalysis, cognitive-behavioral, humanist, transpersonal and Neuro Psychology, as well as Biofeedback y Neurofeedback)
10. A holistic integrating perspective of alternative medicines, namely, resonance with human consciousness.
11. The integration of neurosciences, quantum physics, mathematics, psychology, psychoneuroimmunology, and complexity science at large. [20]
12. Theory of outcome mapping.[10]
13. Sufi Practices and Perspectives (Sufi Community Nur Ashki al Yerráhi of Mexico)
14. Kurt Lewin field theory [19]
15. Ericksonian Psychotherapy Model (Milton Erickson and Jeffrey Zeig). [29]
16. Life, Organizational and Work Team Coaching (Joseph O'Connor and Ricardo Escobar)

In this way, the result is a methodology and a way of practicing brain synchronization, Shintergy style, as an interaction with the different levels of density of vacuum (understood both as the quantum field theory vacuum, and the vacuum of mystic contemplation in this context), focused for high performance both mental and physical.

For short, the combination and training in all the above will be called "Shintergy synchronization". It is a pluripunctual synchronization model (perception over several simultaneous targets) with zero interaction, i.e., there is no actual will of transformation of the self-reality, as it is the case when proprioceptive awareness allows animals to move as desired, with a separation between external stimuli and a reaction, or between planning and executing: it is intended to enter a state where no separation exists between the outward and inward reality, beyond perceived and/or remembered references of time and space. Paradoxically, such state is acquired through attempting to activate all the points

of perception of the subject: internal (interoceptors), external (exteroceptors), and of the self (proprioceptors). Neurologically one of the observed phenomena (see section 2.3) is the switching off of the Default Mode Network which is the neurological network in charge of the self-identity of a person (who am I, where am I, what date is it) [3]. This event creates a paradoxical phenomenon: the subject experiences both a sort of self-dissolution, and yet individuality is preserved.

To fix ideas around testing quantum non-locality concerning consciousness, the Shintergy synchronization was measured when the subject, before starting, integrated a feeling of the desire for sending consciousness in a given direction of time and space. Such desire disappears altogether once actually in the mind state which is the result of applying Shintergy. The directions in time and space was the position of the described laser set up, five meters away from it.

2.3 | Neurological measurements

In this report we are comparing each separated task against the same international database contained in Neuroguide [1]. The neurological measurements were analyzed with the software Z-Builder [1], and the laboratory results refer to the standard ten-twenty nomenclature for the electrodes in the head of the subject[18].

2.4 | Data postprocessing

All data postprocessing was performed with the help of the Wolfram's Mathematica, v.10.

2.4.1 | Direct data plot

The data was taken and plotted directly, so that all graphics show a progressive numbering related with the time stamp of that individual measurement, which in turn, depending on the device, had different sampling rate. On the y axis it is shown the amount of each individual measurement. No units are assigned to either cartesian axis. The graphics contained baseline data and that of the particular experiment itself. The direct observation of the resulting graphic was considered enough to see if any departure existed from the baseline.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | First Laser Experiments (2019)

The collection of the most representative graphics, from experiments made between October and December 2019 is shown. At this time, the described laser was the only operational measuring device.

3.1.1 | Yellow

This section exhibit the influence over a laser, in close proximity of space, and in the present time (called yellow measurements). Each yellow measurement is shown with all and each one of the base lines of that day.

November 15th, 2019

$$\begin{pmatrix} 14:12:21.732 & /01base.txt \\ 15:06:18.828 & /02yellow.txt \end{pmatrix}$$

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 4 /02yellow.txt/01base.txt

November 22nd, 2019

(13:49:03.552 /01base.txt)
(13:56:01.426 /02base.txt)
(12:26:33.405 /03yellow.txt)
(12:36:19.525 /04yellow.txt)
(12:48:29.649 /05yellow.txt)
(12:59:02.283 /06yellow.txt)
(13:08:48.480 /07yellow.txt)

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 5 (/03yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 6 (/03yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 7 (/04yellow.txt /01base.txt)

FIGURE 8 (/04yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 9 (/05yellow.txt /01base.txt)

FIGURE 10 (/05yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

FIGURE 11 (/06yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 12 (/06yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

FIGURE 13 (/07yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 14 $\left(\begin{array}{l} /07yellow.txt \\ /02base.txt \end{array} \right)$

December 5th, 2019

$\left(\begin{array}{ll} 12:47:55.543 & /01base.txt \\ 13:02:02.567 & /02base.txt \\ 13:23:19.046 & /03yellow.txt \end{array} \right)$

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 15 (/03yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 16 (/03yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

December 11th, 2019

(10:02:11.016 /01base.txt)
(10:15:08.893 /02base.txt)
(11:10:04.830 /03yellow.txt)
(11:20:16.765 /04yellow.txt)

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 17 (/03yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 18 (/03yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

FIGURE 19 (/04yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 20 $\left(\begin{array}{l} /04yellow.txt \\ /02base.txt \end{array} \right)$

December 17th, 2019

$$\left(\begin{array}{ll} 11:09:06.676 & /01base.txt \\ 11:18:18.146 & /02base.txt \\ 11:26:51.017 & /03base.txt \\ 11:49:25.166 & /04base.txt \\ 12:08:29.261 & /05base.txt \\ 10:36:15.354 & /08yellow.txt \\ 10:56:58.039 & /09yellow.txt \end{array} \right)$$

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 21 (/08yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 22 (/08yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

FIGURE 23 (/08yellow.txt
/03base.txt)

FIGURE 24 (/08yellow.txt
/04base.txt)

FIGURE 25 (/08yellow.txt
/05base.txt)

FIGURE 26 (/09yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 27 (/09yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 28 (/09yellow.txt /03base.txt)

FIGURE 29 (/09yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 30 (/09yellow.txt)
(/05base.txt)

December 20th, 2019

(09:49:08.986 /01base.txt)
10:02:20.131 /02base.txt
10:16:32.196 /03base.txt
12:54:53.013 /04base.txt
13:28:20.339 /05base.txt
13:51:37.562 /06base.txt
13:40:11.605 /07yellow.txt
14:04:28.732 /08yellow.txt
14:16:43.360 /09yellow.txt
14:29:07.692 /10yellow.txt)

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 31 (/07yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 32 (/07yellow.txt)
(/02base.txt)

FIGURE 33 (/07yellow.txt)
(/03base.txt)

FIGURE 34 (/07yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 35 (/07yellow.txt)
(/05base.txt)

FIGURE 36 (/07yellow.txt)
(/06base.txt)

FIGURE 37 (/08yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 38 (/08yellow.txt)
(/02base.txt)

FIGURE 39 (/08yellow.txt)
(/03base.txt)

FIGURE 40 (/08yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 41 (/08yellow.txt)
(/05base.txt)

FIGURE 42 (/08yellow.txt)
(/06base.txt)

FIGURE 43 (/09yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 44 (/09yellow.txt
/02base.txt)

FIGURE 45 (/09yellow.txt
/03base.txt)

FIGURE 46 (/09yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 47 (/09yellow.txt)
(/05base.txt)

FIGURE 48 (/09yellow.txt
/06base.txt)

FIGURE 49 (/10yellow.txt
/01base.txt)

FIGURE 50 (/10yellow.txt)
(/02base.txt)

FIGURE 51 (/10yellow.txt)
(/03base.txt)

FIGURE 52 (/10yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 53 (/10yellow.txt)
(/05base.txt)

FIGURE 54 $\left(\begin{array}{l} /10yellow.txt \\ /06base.txt \end{array} \right)$

January 10th, 2020

$\left(\begin{array}{ll} 10:10:34.786 & /01base.txt \\ 10:23:50.216 & /02base.txt \\ 11:00:04.860 & /03yellow.txt \\ 11:43:24.402 & /04yellow.txt \\ 12:14:36.772 & /05yellow.txt \end{array} \right)$

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 55 (/03yellow.txt /01base.txt)

FIGURE 56 (/03yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 57 (/04yellow.txt /01base.txt)

FIGURE 58 (/04yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 59 (/05yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 60 (/05yellow.txt)
(/02base.txt)

January 13th, 2020

(10:37:52.706 /01base.txt)
(10:52:12.974 /02base.txt)
(14:12:24.070 /03base.txt)
(11:16:58.019 /04yellow.txt)
(13:41:27.143 /05yellow.txt)

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 61 (/04yellow.txt)
(/01base.txt)

FIGURE 62 (/04yellow.txt)
(/02base.txt)

FIGURE 63 (/04yellow.txt)
(/03base.txt)

FIGURE 64 (/05yellow.txt /01base.txt)

FIGURE 65 (/05yellow.txt /02base.txt)

FIGURE 66 $\left(\begin{array}{l} /05yellow.txt \\ /03base.txt \end{array} \right)$

March 12th, 2020. For this date and for unknown reasons, no base line was registered. The actual experiments are presented, though.

$$\left(\begin{array}{ll} 14:25:35.524 & /04base.txt \\ 14:40:09.415 & /05base.txt \\ 14:54:30.387 & /06yellow.txt \\ 15:14:10.605 & /07yellow.txt \end{array} \right)$$

Initial time stamp of measurements.

FIGURE 67 (/06yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

FIGURE 68 (/07yellow.txt)
(/04base.txt)

3.2 | Neurological and physical measurements simultaneously

These experiments attempted to substantiate a correlation between the access to the Shintergy synchronization according to the different time labels, identifiable through neurological measurements, and the physical measurements. The experiments were performed between March 11th through March 13th, 2020.

3.2.1 | Basal line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: T5 (-0.7) in Delta
- Increase of power: Fp2 (0.6) in Beta, Beta 3 and Hi-Beta; F8 (0.6) in Delta

3.2.2 | Yellow line

neurological measurements

Statistical and significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: O1 (-0.9) in Delta, T5 (-0.6) in Delta.
- Increase of power: Fp1 (0.7) in Gamma, F3 (0.6) in Gamma, C3 (0.6) in Beta 3 and Hi-Beta, C3 (0.9) in Gamma, P3 (0.6) in Gamma, O1 (0.6) in Gamma, F7 (0.6) in Gamma, T3 (0.6) in Beta 1 and Hi-Beta, T3 (0.9) in Gamma, Fz (0.6) in Gamma, F4 (0.7) in Gamma, C4 (0.8) in Gamma, P4 (0.6) in Gamma, O2 (0.6) in Gamma, T4 (0.6) in Gamma, Cz (0.7) in Gamma.

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | General remarks

The graphics of raw data clearly show a deviation from a baseline in many, but not all of the cases, in a qualitative and sometimes markedly in a quantitative way as well. In the case of laser light, the behavior is non-optical, since in some instances the brilliance decreases, but in others *increase*, as it can be appreciated by the reading of the received voltage.

The change in brilliancy of the laser, as it was implied, at the beginning was considered to be of optical nature, but no known optical theories seem to explain away satisfactorily all that is observed.

Although it is apparent that the usage of Shintergy synchronization has a close correlation to these phenomena, even having the neurological evidence, there is no detailed mechanical explanation on how it occurs, nor how it can be finely-tuned on its control, if it is possible a control at all; this is mentioned, because as it was mentioned before, the Shintergy synchronization does require an abandonment of an intention of control.

4.2 | Neurological measurements

In this section it is discussed the neurological meaning of the electrode measurements.

4.2.1 | Yellow condition (present time, 5 meters apart from devices)

The decrease in the power of Delta is concentrated in the upper right parietal region (AB 7, 5), which could be associated with the decrease in visuospatial processing, with the perception of personal space and the sensation of "I".

The increase in Delta power is bilaterally concentrated in the prefrontal region (AB 10), which could be associated with modulation and inhibition of impulses and behavior.

The increase in Gamma power is mainly concentrated in the upper left parietal region (AB 7, 5) and the left motor and premotor region (AB 4, 8), which could be associated with visuospatial processing, the perception of space personal and the feeling of "I", self-monitoring and imagination of movement.

5 | CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Shintergy synchronization seems in close correlation to the observed phenomena in the laser measurements, although no mechanical, detailed explanation (cause-effect) can be offered.

Future exploration concerning the stability of the Shintergy state of synchronization should be considered.

acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the work of Dr. Dolores Gaxiola, MD, for the neurological measurements and clinical interpretation, and the assistance of Alma Lidia Torres Álvarez, Alberto Rojas Medina BSc and Eng. Erik Iván Cruz Mendoza for their technical support. Dr. Ortiz-Tapia would like to thank all his teachers of any kind.

Supporting Information

As it was mentioned, further supporting information can be found at the following page <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Gravitational-Anomalies-and-Shintergy-brain-synchronization>

references

- [1] Biver, C. J., 2020: *Neuroguide*.
URL <https://appliedneuroscience.com/neuroguide/>
- [2] Briggs, J. and F. D. Peat, 1989: *Turbulent mirror: An illustrated guide to chaos theory and the science of wholeness*. Harper-Collins Publishers.
- [3] Buckner, R. L., J. R. Andrews-Hanna, and D. L. Schacter, 2008: The brain's default network: anatomy, function, and relevance to disease. *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*

- [4] Bueno, J., ????: personal communication.
- [5] Bueno-Shin, J. L., 2019: personal communication.
- [6] Capra, F., 2010: *The Tao of physics: An exploration of the parallels between modern physics and eastern mysticism*. Shambhala Publications.
- [7] Caycedo, A., 1973: *Diccionario abreviado de sofrología y relajación dinámica: términos, vocablos, diseños, esquemas, planificación [and others]*. Ediciones Aura.
- [8] Conway, J. and S. Kochen, 2006: The free will theorem. *Foundations of Physics*, **36**, no. 10, 1441–1473.
- [9] Deussen, P., 1997: *Sixty Upanishads of the Veda*. Motilal Banarsidass Publ.
- [10] Earl, S., F. Carden, and T. Smutylo, 2001: *Outcome mapping: Building learning and reflection into development programs*. IDRC, Ottawa, ON, CA.
- [11] Grinberg-Zylberbaum, J., M. Delaflor, M. S. Arellano, et al., 1993: Human communication and the electrophysiological activity of the brain. *Subtle Energies & Energy Medicine Journal Archives*, **3**, no. 3.
- [12] Haramain, N., W. D. Brown, and A. V. Baker, 2016: The unified spacememory network: from cosmogenesis to consciousness. *NeuroQuantology*, **14**, no. 4, 657–671.
- [13] Haramain, N., M. Hyson, and E. Rauscher, 2008: Scale unification: a universal scaling law for organized matter. *Proceedings of the Unified Theories Conference*, Sec, volume 4, 11–16.
- [14] Hesse, M. B., 1955: Action at a distance in classical physics. *Isis*, **46**, no. 4, 337–353.
- [15] Hofstadter, D. R. et al., 1979: *Gödel, Escher, Bach: an eternal golden braid*, volume 13. Basic books New York.
- [16] Hughes, J. M., 2016: *Arduino: a technical reference: a handbook for technicians, engineers, and makers*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- [17] Jhanananda, S., 2011: *The yoga-sūtra of patañjali*.
URL <https://web.archive.org/web/20110504200949/http://www.greatwesternvehicle.org/vedic/jhananandaysutra.htm>
- [18] Klem, G. H., H. Lüders, H. H. Jasper, and C. Elger, 1999: The ten-twenty electrode system of the international federation. the international federation of clinical neurophysiology. *Electroencephalography and clinical neurophysiology. Supplement*, **52**, 3–6.
- [19] Lewin, K., 1951: *Field theory in social science: selected theoretical papers (Edited by Dorwin Cartwright.)*. Harpers.
- [20] Newman, M. E., 2011: Complex systems: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1112.1440*.
- [21] Penrose, R., 1989: *The Emperor's New Mind*. New York: Penguin Books.
- [22] Rambachan, A., 2006: *The Advaita worldview: God, world, and humanity*. SUNY Press.
- [23] Renk, K. F., 2012: *Basics of laser physics*. Springer.
- [24] Reynolds, J. M., 2020: *The history of bön*.
URL <http://shenten.org/yungdrung-bon/77-history>
- [25] Saari, D., 2016: Dynamics and the dark matter mystery. *SciAm News*.
- [26] Woodward, F. L., 2005: *The Book of the Kindred Sayings (Saṃyutta-nikāya) Or Grouped Suttas:(Mahā-vagga)*. Motilal Banarsidass Publisher.

-
- [27] Wozniak, J. A., S. Wu, and H. Wang, 1991: *Yan Xin Qigong and the Contemporary Sciences*. International Yan Xin Qigong Association.
- [28] Young, B.-L., 2017: A survey of dark matter and related topics in cosmology. *Frontiers of Physics*, **12**, no. 2, 121201.
- [29] Zeig, J. K., 1985: *Ericksonian psychotherapy: Clinical applications*, volume 2. Bruner Meisel U.